

Achieving work-personal life balance and the importance of mentorship for women in crop science

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Background

Finding the right work-personal life balance can represent a big challenge for women in crop science in finding a daily equilibrium between personal life and diverse professional commitments (field and lab operations, meetings, writing scientific outputs or proposals, professional relationships, offering and receiving training, etc.). An important resource to help in the quest for balance between work and personal life is identifying a mentor who can provide insights and ideas to support female (and male) scientists reach professional goals without sacrificing personal interests on the way. On 9th September 2022, Maria Itria Ibba and Carolina Rivera-Amado, both wheat scientists at CIMMYT, led an open discussion on work-personal life balance and mentoring, with special attention on the experiences of women in crop science. We used two resources in order to stimulate the discussion: an interview piece about mentoring in science and a podcast about work and personal life balance. A compilation of comments, positions, ideas and further actions were raised at the meeting and are presented in this article. We hope this will be food for thought to the women in science community at CIMMYT and others interested in this topic.

Work-personal life balance

During the meeting, we presented a summary of a podcast (Science vs Burnout: Can we fix Work - <https://gimletmedia.com/shows/science-vs/o2h8rra>) which talks about the challenges of achieving work-life balance as well as providing some practical advice. The podcast highlighted that overwork, poor work-life balance and work burnout are associated with a continuous and extreme form of stress that could have serious repercussions not only on our psychological health but also our physical health. Scientific studies have shown that people who are affected by severe burnout have a smaller pre-frontal cortex which is associated with a reduced ability to focus, concentrate, and remember things. Also, people under such constant stress, are more likely to suffer from heart disease, have a weaker immune system and experience teeth grinding during sleep. The reasons that could lead to work burnout are different such as

the feeling that we are not doing properly our job, the assignment of excessive tasks, not being appreciated, and a low salary.

Working from home during the pandemic, has often increased this phenomenon due to the difficulty to switch off from work. This is also due to the increased number of hours spent “on the job” compared to when working in the office. These are currently some of the major reasons for people quitting their positions which makes the improvement of work-life balance one of the major points that employers and companies should consider. In the attempt to reduce the risk of work burnout, Iceland implemented a reduced working hours per week schedule without affecting the salary of the staff. Implementation of such policies showed that workers were less stressed, were at a lower risk of burnout and had an improved health and work-life balance. This, and many other measures, could be readily implemented by organizations like CIMMYT where, starting from the institutional level down to the individual level, a healthy working culture which respects the personal lives of staff should be promoted.

The subjects discussed in the podcasts were used to stimulate the conversation among the participants to try to better understand some of the reasons behind an imbalance between work and personal life and burnout within our institution and to try to identify some methods to cope with it and to reduce its incidence. Below we compiled some comments shared during the discussion.

What solutions or approaches can be used to cope with work stress? How could we improve work-personal life balance?

- **Protect your personal time.** It is of paramount importance to really use our time outside work to ourselves, to disconnect and have some hobbies that fulfill us and distract us from the duties of work. To do this, it is important to first know ourselves, understand the reasons why it is hard to respect our personal time and to define some ways to be able to disconnect.
- **Accept the right to disconnect.** Often, due to the imbedded and common over-working culture of the institution, we could feel ashamed to take time for ourselves during vacation. The time off work is and should be used as a time for our personal life which, if used, would benefit our health and eventually our productivity.
- **Promote a culture that encourages work-life balance.** When we are the only ones trying to improve our work-life balance but the rest of our colleagues, supervisors and leaders of the institution do not, it is hard to comply with fixed working hours and to disconnect from work. Everyone, starting from the leaders and supervisors, should apply some “rules” that respect staff’s personal time.
- **Communicate your feelings and emotions.** Often, when we feel overwhelmed by our jobs and/or by situations that are conducive to work burnout, it is hard to express our feelings and to communicate to our supervisors our concerns. The reasons associated with this tendency could be multiple, including culture, personality and, in some cases, fear of losing the position. Learning to say no or to discuss such topics with our supervisors could be of great help, especially when the supervisor does not realize they are assigning too many tasks to their staff or that it is putting too much pressure on them.

What are some of the causes of excessive work stress?

- **Lack of effective work organization and planning.** In some cases, especially when we are assigned new tasks or when we have multiple tasks to conduct, it is hard to effectively organize our

activities. This will eventually lead to excessive work stress and work burnout, especially when deadlines are approaching. Mentorship and systematic work planning and prioritization could help resolving this problematic issue. It is also important to promote a culture of important over urgent tasks, of course urgent tasks can appear from time to time but they should not be the rule.

- **Assignment of too many tasks/understaffing.** Often, tasks assigned by supervisors are associated only with some theoretical percentage of time that the employee will use to conduct them. Most of the time, the time required to perform them is greater than expected which eventually leads to working long hours at the expense of the personal time. This problem could also be associated with a lack of staff available to conduct the work with the result that most of the activities will eventually have to be conducted by few people. And, because some people have more reservations to say “no” when tasks are assigned.
- **Systemic limitations.** Protection of personal time can only be effective if, when out of work, it is possible to disconnect and delegate some tasks to other colleagues. However, in some cases, it is hard to do so and there are some administrative procedures that require the action of specific people without the possibility to delegate. Right delegation mechanisms should be in place at the institutions, as everyone deserves to fully disconnect from time to time. Even if such tasks might not take too long to conduct, they eventually force the staff to stay mentally connected with the work thus impacting effective work-life balance.

Mentoring for women in science

During the meeting, we also presented an interview piece with the audience with Judith Walters, Chief of the Neurophysiological Pharmacology Section in the National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke (NINDS) in the US. Here we present a small summary, more can be read at <https://irp.nih.gov/catalyst/v23i2/the-science-of-mentoring-women-in-science>. Judith was one of the first women to get a PhD in Pharmacology from the University of Yale, she attributes much of her early career success to having good mentors during critical times but also to providing and receiving mentoring from peers at the same career stage. Judith’s current mentees describe her as available and accessible, having an open-door policy, welcoming interruptions and hosting informal weekly lab meetings. Katrina Furth, a graduate student at Boston University, feels less intimidated taking early manuscript drafts to Judith than to other mentors. On the topic of multiple mentors, Judith agrees that it’s not always an easy balance and wouldn’t recommend it for everyone, although the benefit is getting ideas and techniques from people with different strengths and backgrounds. Kristin Dupre, a post-doc in Judith’s lab directs her own mentoring toward next career steps and does not believe she mentors women versus men differently but rather adapt her mentoring style based on the individual.

In respect to working mothers, Judith recalls although she had no access to maternity leave and lactation rooms, although thinks it was easier when she was younger because childcare was far less expensive than is today. Although Judith thinks society is more approving of men making a more equal contribution to parenting tasks than in the past, and they are contributing more, a lot still ends up on the new mother’s plate.

After presenting a summary of the article, we asked some questions to the audience. Below we compiled some comments shared during the discussion of participants present during our session.

Do you think women in science require a special type of mentoring? Would mentoring help improving work-personal life balance?

- It is important to help early career scientists to network -especially women- since environments where scientific discussion happen (e.g. conferences, internal meetings) can be more hostile to women than to men (e.g. people, especially senior scientists paying less attention to young women scientists).
- The mentoring approach should be based on the individual, not on age, gender or position. For example, mentors' approaches can vary even if all mentees are early career female scientists. This is due to differences in personality, level of achievement and fulfillment, personal choices.
- Peer to peer mentorship among women in similar circumstances can be extremely helpful, for example, female scientist who are new mothers and are particularly struggling to find the right work-life balance.
- Positive reinforcement among and for women in science is very encouraging.
- All participants reflected on the value of mentors, and on finding mentors that are a good match for both stage of scientific development but also personal values. Using shared values or intentions is a good way to develop a holistic mentee-mentor relationship.

What is your position about getting mentoring from your direct supervisor?

- Most people agreed that although receiving mentoring from supervisors can be helpful since they are best aware of the mentees day-to-day activities, they can have a more limited vision of activities or opportunities outside of the current scope. They also tend to be biased by the need for staff members to deliver on specific projects.
- Some people suggested to look for mentors outside of your main supervisor circle or even outside the organization where you are, to get fresh insights and solutions to the mentee's concerns and to look for new learning opportunities.

Any advice to look for mentors and maintain healthy and productive relationships with mentors?

- Make a list of potentially useful peer interactions, try to keep contact regularly with them.
- Prioritize areas or topics that you need to strengthen (e.g. writing scientific articles, conflict resolution, etc.).
- Set objectives and expectations when starting a mentee-mentor relationship or commitment. It should fall to the mentee to let the mentor know what they need or hope to achieve, and to keep the relationship active.
- The open-door policy does not work for every mentor, some of them have strict agendas and commitments, therefore there can be a need for planned meeting schedules. Discuss with your mentor the right way of interaction that works for both parties.
- Feedback is a gift, be open and grateful when receiving it. Ask for formal training to give feedback to your supervisor or institution.
- Try peer to peer mentorship, it is helpful to receive feedback from peers that are at similar career stage and/or going through similar issues or having successful career/personal outcomes.
- Commit to the mentoring program, save space and time for it, no matters how informal/non-official it is.
- Look for mentors at any time of your career path, mentors can always challenge you and help you improve.

Topics for further discussion and action (both, work-life balance and mentoring)

- Start a peer to peer mentoring program or protocol, at least as a suggestion to early career CIMMYT scientists.
- Ask human resources for opportunities to get training to be a mentor, especially to people currently supervising scientists.